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Highlights

- It is evaluated the impact of ship traffic and harbour activities on aerosol.
- Contribution to PAHs concentrations of harbour-industrial emissions was estimated
- Harbour contributes for 9.3% to PM_{2.5} and for 39% to particle number concentration.
- Harbour-industrial emissions contribute for 56% to total PAHs concentrations.

Contribution of harbour activities and ships traffic to PM_{2.5}, particle number concentrations and PAHs in a port-city of the Mediterranean Sea (Italy)

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Abstract

In this work it is reported an assessment of the impact of ship traffic and related harbour activities (loading/unloading of ships and hotelling in harbour) on PM_{2.5}, particle number concentrations (PNC) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) concentrations in the port-city of Brindisi (South-Eastern Italy). PM_{2.5} and PNC concentrations shows a clear daily pattern correlated with daily ship traffic pattern in the harbour. High temporal resolution measurements and correlations with wind direction were used to estimate the average direct contribution to measured concentrations of this source. The average relative contribution of ship traffic and manouvering was in 7.4% ($\pm 0.5\%$) for PM_{2.5}, and in 26% ($\pm 1\%$) for PNC. A further analysis performed including the contribution of harbour-related activities gave a contribution of 9.3% ($\pm 0.5\%$) to PM_{2.5} and 39% ($\pm 1\%$) to PNC. Air from the harbour/industrial sector was richer in PAHs (5.34 ng/m³) than generic air of Brindisi (3.89 ng/m³). The major compounds were phenanthrene, fluoranthene and pyrene, but the congeners profiles were different in the two typologies of samples: air from the harbour/industrial sector was richer, with respect to other wind directions, in phenanthrene and fluorene, which are the most abundant PAHs from ship emissions. Results showed that PAHs are mainly in the gas phase. The gas-particle distribution was characterized by the lighter PAHs associated to the gaseous phase and higher molecular weight congeners mostly present in the particulate phase. The general contribution of the harbour-industrial source to PAHs was 56% (29-87%). The harbour influenced PAHs concentration especially contributing to acenaphtylene,

1 acenaphtene, fluorene, phenanthrene and benzo[*a*]pyrene. Total Carcinogenic Activity calculated
2 using TEFs was slightly higher in samples from the harbour/industrial sector than in those from
3 other wind directions. Particulate matter was characterized by a higher carcinogenic activity than
4 gaseous phase, due to the gas-particle distribution of congeners.
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8 **Highlights**

- 9 • It is evaluated the impact of ship traffic and harbour activities on aerosol.
- 10 • Contribution to PAHs concentrations of harbour-industrial emissions was estimated
- 11 • Harbour contributes for 9.3% to PM2.5 and for 39% to particle number concentration.
- 12 • Harbour-industrial emissions contribute for 56% to total PAHs concentrations.

13 **Keywords**

14 Ship traffic emissions, harbour, particle number concentration, polycyclic aromatics hydrocarbons
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20 **1. Introduction**

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22 Global commerce is flourishing and the demand for ports services has increased significantly
23 in the last years (Zhao et al., 2013). The growing volume of passengers and freight is putting a great
24 stress on ports and the inland supporting systems and infrastructure. Even though these
25 infrastructural facilities have a great impact on economic growth of coastal areas their impact on the
26 surrounding environment is growing more and more (Dalsøren et al., 2009). This is particularly true
27 considering that, at global level, land-based emissions of airborne pollutants are decreasing but ship
28 emissions are increasing leading to potential negative effects on health and climate and social
29 welfare. The emissions from ships may compromise the air quality during hotelling and
30 manouvering in harbours and during transit along the coast. The health effects of air pollution from
31 ports and ships may include asthma, other respiratory diseases, cardiovascular disease, lung cancer
32 and premature death (Corbett et al., 2007; Dockery and Pope, 2006; Xia et al., 2004; Delfino et al.,
33 2005). A recent study by the California Air Resources Board (CARB, 2006) estimated that diesel
34 particulate matter emissions from the Port of Los Angeles and Long Beach increase the cancer risk
35 for the 60% of the neighbouring population (Kuwayama T. et al., 2013). Incidence of asthma,
36 among other diseases, could be linked to exposure to ultrafine particles (UFPs - approximately
37 <100 nm in diameter) (Pekkanen et al., 1997; Li et al., 2003). UFPs deposit with high efficiency in
38 the lower human lung due to their size (Gong et al., 2007). Although UFPs constitute just a small
39 fraction of PM2.5 mass concentration, high temporal resolution measurements of particle number
40 concentration could give more detailed information with respect to PM2.5 concentration to assess
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1 potential risks associated to specific emissions. In urban environments and, in particular, in port
2 cities and coastal areas several sources of air pollution can act together (Kim et al., 2002;
3 Westerdahl et al., 2005): ship traffic, industry, rail traffic, and usual sources such as residential
4 emissions (Kleeman et al., 1999; Schauer et al., 2001) because harbours are often located near cities
5 and industrial complexes. While vehicular traffic received a great deal of attention as source of air
6 pollution in urban environment (Jarvi et al., 2009; Nemitz et al., 2008, Schmidt and Klemm, 2008;
7 Contini et al., 2012), the role played by the shipping sources has received much less attention. The
8 economic costs of these emissions is estimated at between 10 and 21.5 million Euro per year and
9 the future annual costs imposed by pollution from ships at berth in the port will depend on future
10 traffic at the harbours, engine technology and fuel type (McArthur and Osland, 2013). A recent
11 source apportionment study performed in Barcelona (Amato et al., 2009) reports a mean annual
12 contribution from heavy fuel oil combustion (mainly ship emissions) of 5% and 8% of PM10 and
13 PM1 respectively. In a study conducted by Pandolfi et al. (2011), PM10 and PM2.5 data were
14 collected around the Bay of Algeciras in southern Spain. It was estimated that the direct
15 contribution from shipping in the bay of Algeciras for PM10 concentration was between 3% and
16 7% and between 5% and 10% for PM2.5 concentration. Agrawal et al. (2009) found that primary
17 PM2.5 contributions from vessels in the harbour of Los Angeles range from 8.8% at the monitoring
18 location closest to the port to 1.4% monitored 80 km inland. In Turkey, the shipping emissions in
19 coastal regions with heavy ship traffic were investigated in two papers: the first study was carried
20 out in the Candarli Gulf (Deniz et al., 2010) and the second study at the Ambarli Port (Deniz and
21 Kilic, 2009). In this works total emissions from ships in the Candarli Gulf and the port of Ambarli
22 was estimated for particulate matter as 57.4 tons/year and 36 tons/year, respectively, using
23 numerical simulations of a dispersion model with real topographic and meteorological conditions of
24 the harbour region. Healy et al. (2009) characterized particle number concentration from hotelling
25 ship emissions in the Port of Cork in Ireland. In this study, the size and composition of freshly
26 emitted individual ship exhaust particles was investigated and an increase in mass concentrations of
27 sulphate, elemental carbon and PM2.5 were observed during these events. An international study
28 carried out by Moldanova et al. (2009) investigated particles emission from a ship diesel engine
29 fuelled with heavy fuel oil. The investigation of the emitted particle matter included mass, size
30 distribution, chemical composition of the PM. In the cited work, the emission factor found for PM
31 was 5.3 g/kg fuel and the mass size distribution showed a bimodal shape with two maxima: one in
32 the accumulation mode with mean particle diameter around 0.5 μm and one in the coarse mode at
33 around 7 μm .

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Contini et al. (2011) estimated in the urban area of Venice in Italy the direct influence of ship traffic on atmospheric PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). In this work authors developed a new methodology based on high temporal resolution measurements coupled with wind direction information and the database of ship passages. The study showed that direct contribution of ships traffic to PM_{2.5} and to PM₁₀ ranges from 1% up to 8%. The heavy fuel oils used for propulsion by most vessels have a high content of sulphur (2.4% – 2.7%) and PAHs (EPA, 2006; Endresen et al., 2005). Thus aerosol emissions associated to ship engines are characterized by significant content of sulphates, typically associated to secondary inorganic aerosol generated by the use of heavy fuel oil, and traces of metals like V and Ni, typically considered as a specific tracer of primary emissions from ships (Minguillon et al., 2008; Stortini et al., 2009c). There is a debate on the possibility of using better qualities of marine fuels in order to cut down increased emissions due to the predicted growth in seaborne trade (Eyring et al, 2010). The use of these oils will considerably reduce emission of SO₂, PM, PAHs and NO_x by around 5% (Copper and Gustavsson, 2004). As reported in Schembari et al. (2012), the observations in five Mediterranean harbours (period 2009-2010) gave strong evidence of reduction of ambient SO₂ concentrations in concomitance with the impact of the European Union directive 2005/33/EC that regulates the emission of SO₂ from ships in European harbours from January 2010. In Europe and in the United States, the lawmakers worked on implementation of environmental directives focused on the abatement of ship emissions. The State of California approved an Emission Reduction Plan and Goods Movement in 2006 with the goal to reduce emission to 2001 levels by 2010 (Kuwayama et al., 2013). Prior to implementation of the control program port trucks accounted for approximately 56% of the elemental carbon concentration in particulate matter. After the implementation of the control program, port trucks contribution is 23% of the ambient elemental carbon concentrations. In present work it is reported an assessment of the impact of ship traffic and related harbour activities on PM_{2.5}, particle number concentrations and PAHs concentrations in the port-city of Brindisi. The work was developed within the framework of the CESAPO project (Contribution of Emission Sources on the Air quality of the POrt-cities in Greece and Italy – www.cesapo.upatras.gr).

51 **2. Measurement sites**

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The measurement campaign was structured as an Intensive Observation Period (IOP) in which several instruments at high and low temporal resolution were run together in the harbour area of Brindisi in the South-eastern part of Italy (Apulia region). Experimental activities were carried out in the period from 10th June to 22th October 2012. The harbour is located in the east side of the city (Figure 1a). It has a yearly traffic of more than 9.5 million tons of goods, over 520,000 passengers

1 and over 175,000 vehicles (source: Brindisi Port Authority). The Brindisi area is characterized by a
2 quite complicated scheme of emission sources including urban emissions (88,500 inhabitants),
3 harbour, petrochemical and power plant emissions. The area includes an international airport,
4 located at 3 km NNE of the urban area and about 2 km N of the measurement site. At south of our
5 site a large industrial area is present. It is characterized by the presence of an important
6 petrochemical plant (production of polyethylene, PVC and other polymers) of a pharmaceutical
7 industry (Sanofi-Aventis), of an industrial waste incinerator (Veolia) of an industry for construction
8 of airplanes components (Fiat Avio) and of several artisan activities. The area of Brindisi is
9 included in the list of SIN (National Sites of Interest) for relevant and potentially dangerous
10 pollution, according to Italian Legislation.
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18 The internal harbour area of Brindisi is more than 700.000 m² for a total of 2 km of docks that
19 could accommodate at the same time up to 8 Ro-Ro ships. This part of the harbour is mainly
20 dedicated to tourist activities and it includes the passenger terminal. The intermediate part of the
21 harbour (1,200,000 m² with 3 km of docks) is dedicated to commercial ships. The outer part of
22 harbour (Costa Morena) is dedicated to the traffic of coal-ships, bulk carriers, and small general
23 cargo.
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29 A Mobile Laboratory was located inside the harbour very close to passengers station
30 (Terminal Passeggeri). This station (40°38'43.32''N - 17°57'36.39''E) was devoted to high
31 temporal resolution measurements of PM_{2.5} and particle number concentrations. The site is facing
32 (about 40 m) the harbour water and ferry boat docks as shown in Figure 1b. A second measurement
33 site was installed in the area, at approximately 1300 m from the position of Mobile Laboratory
34 (Figure 1a), to perform a complete long-term chemical characterization of PAHs (Polycyclic
35 Aromatic Hydrocarbons). This site was located on the roof of the building of the Consorzio per
36 l'Area di Sviluppo Industriale (ASI) (40°38'05.78''N, 17°57'10.00''E) in Brindisi at about 13 m
37 from ground level. The ASI site was equipped with two high volume samplers, one of them with a
38 wind selective capability (Figure 2b).
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49 **3. PM_{2.5} and particle number concentrations (PNC) measurements**

50 The Mobile Laboratory was equipped with a micrometeorological station placed at 10 m
51 above the ground on a telescopic mast. It was composed of a three-dimensional ultrasonic
52 anemometer (R3, Gill Instruments, Lymington, UK), operating at 100 Hz in calibrated mode, for
53 measuring wind velocity and sonic temperature. Additional instruments have been used with their
54 outputs sampled and digitalized by the anemometer itself synchronously with wind velocity
55 measurements: specifically, a low response thermo-hygrometer Rotronic MP100A (Campbell
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1 Scientific) was used to detect relative humidity and air temperature; a fast-response (1 Hz) optical
2 detector pDR-1200 (Personal Data logging Real time Aerosol Monitor, by Thermo Electron Corp.,
3 Franklin, MA) to measure PM_{2.5} mass concentrations (Donateo et al., 2006); a Condensation
4 Particle Counter (CPC, Grimm Aerosol Model 5.403) to measure (1 Hz) the total particle number
5 concentrations. The pDR-1200 was operating with a pump for active sampling using a cyclone (2.5
6 µm cut-off at the 4 l/min flow rate used, model GK2.05). Sampling flow was checked periodically
7 with a flow meter in such a way that a constant flow of 4 l/min is kept throughout the period of
8 campaign. It was verified that the zero of the nephelometer can change of about 5-6 µg/m³ over a
9 period of about 3-4 weeks and this offset was corrected in post-processing. The pDR-1200 was
10 placed inside a small aerated outdoor box (Figure 2a) fixed at the top of a tripod (3 m height above
11 ground) and air samples were collected through a 30 cm stainless tube, fixed above top cover of the
12 outdoor box. The pDR-1200 uses infrared radiation scattering (880 nm) for concentration
13 measurements and it is influenced by high values in relative humidity (RH>70%), because the water
14 vapour changes dimension, density and optical properties of the particles (Sioutas et al., 2000,
15 Chakrabarti et al., 2004) and modifying the scattering and absorption coefficients of particles and
16 consequently the response of the optical detector used (Chakrabarti et al., 2004). Therefore,
17 measured concentrations have been corrected to take into account the role of RH using the
18 correction procedure developed in (Donateo et al., 2006). To test the quality of optical
19 measurements of PM_{2.5} a comparison of the results obtained with the pDR-1200 with daily PM_{2.5}
20 measurements taken with the reference gravimetric method has been performed. Results indicate an
21 average PM_{2.5} concentration of 16.6 µg/m³ (with standard deviation of 6.7 µg/m³) for the pDR-
22 1200 and of 16 µg/m³ (with standard deviation of 5.9 µg/m³) for the gravimetric method with a
23 Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.8 between the two series.
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42 The CPC (Figure 2b) output was connected to the analog inputs of the anemometer using a
43 digital-to-analog converter interface opportunely developed at ISAC-CNR. Fast-response data
44 collection software, developed by ISAC-CNR in LabWindows CVI® (by National Instruments®)
45 environment, was used. Aerosol was sampled through a 50 cm long sampling inlet with a stainless
46 steel rain protection of 26 mm internal diameter, on the roof of the Mobile Laboratory at 2.5 m
47 above the ground. A pump (Tecora Bravo H-plus) was used to maintain a flow-rate of about 30
48 l/min in the inlet tube. A portion of 1.5 l/min was taken from the main flow at the end of the inlet
49 tube using a 50 cm long conductive plastic tube (6 mm internal diameter) and injected into the CPC.
50 Sampled air flow went through a dryer to reduce water vapour concentration before it arrives to the
51 CPC. Dryer was designed and developed in our laboratory, it works using silica gel cartridge that
52 were replaced every two days. It is long 24 cm with an internal diameter of 2 cm. The particle
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1 losses were calculated according to the formulation reported in Hinds (1999). The total counting
2 efficiency was calculated as the product between the penetration factor and the counting efficiency
3 of the CPC obtained from Heim et al. (2004). Results show that the cut-off diameter (at 50%
4 efficiency) is around 9 nm in the used configuration, thereby, the system was measuring particle
5 number concentration in the range 9-1000 nm (the latter is the upper limit of the CPC).
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9 The measurement station was equipped with a network video camera (AXIS 221) able to
10 operate during night and day collecting photos every 30 s of the harbour areas. This was used to
11 monitor departure/arrival of ships in the observed area and vehicles passing in the area facing the
12 dock. Ship traffic data from the Avvisatore Marittimo di Brindisi and from MarineTraffic.com were
13 also used in order to have a complete database of ship traffic in the area studied. The video camera
14 was used to exactly synchronize the database of ship traffic with concentration measurements.
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22 **4. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) measurements**

23 At ASI measurement site, two high-volume samplers (AirFlowPUF, Analitica Strumenti, Italy
24 and Tish Environmental Inc., USA) were installed. One of them was conditioned by the wind
25 direction: it was programmed to turn on when the wind was blowing from the harbour/industrial
26 sector (NNW-E), thus collecting only PAHs from that sector. Simultaneously the second sampler
27 was collecting air from all directions. PAHs sampling was conducted from June to September 2012;
28 13 samples and 6 blanks were collected with the frequency listed in Table 1.
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34 Details about the analytical method were widely described elsewhere (Contini et al., 2011).
35 Briefly, gaseous PAHs were collected on pre-cleaned polyurethane foams (PUFs) and PAHs in
36 particulate phase on pre-combusted quartz fibre filters (QFFs). This method allows to obtain
37 information not only on the whole concentration of PAHs in the area, but also on the gas-particle
38 distribution of each congener. Extraction and purification were conducted using automatic systems.
39 Pressurized Liquid Extractor (PLE, Fluid Management System Inc., USA) was used to extract
40 PAHs from the samples, using the following conditions: *n*-hexane/dichloromethane mixture (1:1,
41 *v/v*), three cycles, 100 °C, 1000 psi, 7 min of static duration; purification was performed using the
42 PowerPrep system (Fluid Management System Inc., USA), with 30 mL *n*-hexane and 30 mL of *n*-
43 hexane/dichloromethane mixture (1:1, *v/v*) to elute the extract. For quantitative purpose, three ¹³C-
44 labelled PAHs (¹³C-acenaphthylene, ¹³C-phenanthrene, ¹³C-benzo[*a*]pyrene) were spiked before
45 extraction and ¹³C-chrysene was added after purification as recovery standard (internal standard
46 method). Samples were analyzed by gas chromatography, coupled with mass spectrometry. Field
47 blanks were used to determine any contamination during sample handling and preparation. PUFs
48 and QFFs samples were corrected for the corresponding average field blank. 15 of the priority
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PAHs, as indicated by US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) were determined: acenaphthylene (ACY), acenaphthene (ACE), fluorene (FL), phenanthrene (PHE), anthracene (ANT), fluoranthene (FLT), pyrene (PYR), benzo[*a*]anthracene (BaA), chrysene (CHR), benzo[*b*]fluoranthene (BbF), benzo[*k*]fluoranthene (BkF), benzo[*a*]pyrene (BaP), benzo[*g,h,i*]perylene (BghiP), indeno[1,2,3-*c,d*]pyrene (IcdP), dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene (BahA).

The total PAHs concentration (Σ PAHs), as the sum of all congeners in both phases, was taken into account for a first evaluation of the contribution of the harbour/industrial area to the PAHs. The coefficient ε (Equation 1) was used to evaluate the percentage of PAHs coming from the harbour/industrial area, compared to pollutants coming from all directions. It did not consider the distribution of wind direction and intensity, but it represented the absolute value of pollutants intake referred to a hypothetical person, staying in the sampling site, in the specific measurement period.

$$\varepsilon(\%) = (Q_p / Q_{360}) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where: Q_p is the Σ PAHs quantity during sampling (48h or 72h), in aerosol coming from the harbour area, obtained from the wind-select sampler; Q_{360} is the Σ PAHs quantity during sampling (48h or 72h), in aerosol coming from all directions, obtained from the other sampler. ε is a good coefficient to evaluate the ship traffic influence in a specific site and period (local effect of the harbour/industrial sector), but it is largely influenced by the local meteorology and, specifically, the frequency of occurrence of wind direction from the harbour/industrial sector. Thus, ε was not useful to make a source apportionment of PAHs nor it could be exploited to compare the direct effect of the harbour/industrial emissions over the years. For this reason the coefficient χ (general effect of the harbour, Equation 2) has been developed. In this case, for both sectors, every contribution to the total PAHs concentration is normalized for the effective sampling time, obtaining a value independent from wind strength and direction.

$$\chi(\%) = Q_{P,h} (Q_{P,h} + Q_{A,h})^{-1} = \frac{Q_p}{h_p} \left(\frac{Q_p}{h_p} + \frac{Q_{360} - Q_p}{h_{360} - h_p} \right)^{-1} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

where: $Q_{P,h}$ is the hourly Σ PAHs amount, in aerosol coming from the harbour/industrial sector; $Q_{A,h}$ is the hourly Σ PAHs amount, in aerosol coming from all directions, with the exception of the harbour/industrial sector; Q_p is the Σ PAHs quantity during sampling (48h or 72h), in aerosol coming from the harbour/industrial area; Q_{360} is the Σ PAHs quantity during sampling (48h or 72h),

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2 in aerosol coming from all directions; h_p is the sampling time (hours) of the wind-select sampler;
3 h_{360} is the sampling time (hours) of the other sampler.
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5. Meteorology in the area during the IOP

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7 The wind speed was measured by the ultrasonic anemometer at 10 m height and available on
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9 30 minutes average. During the campaign the wind velocity was relatively high, ranging from 1m/s
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11 to 14 m/s. The average temperature varied between about 13 °C and 40 °C, and the average relative
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13 humidity varied between 14% and 95%. The meteorology of this measurement site is characterized
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15 by episodes of strong wind blowing from the Adriatic Sea associated to north-westerly north-
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17 easterly (NW-NE) directions. The predominant wind directions at the site are north-westerly (N-
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19 NW) as shown in Figure 3. Winds blowing from N-NW sector are the strongest having an average
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21 speed of about 4.8 m/s to be compared with the average speed of 3.4 m/s considering all wind
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23 directions. During the campaign the site is downwind of the potential ship/harbour sources for 48%
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25 of the time. The wind calms (winds lower than 0.5 m/s) were 0.9% of the measurement period and
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27 the low winds (winds lower than 1 m/s) were 5.9% of the measurement period. The local
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29 meteorology does not have the characteristics of breeze because there is not a clear daily cycle of
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31 wind direction, rather, there are relatively extended periods with wind coming from the NW-NE
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33 sector or from the S-SW sector.
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6. PM10, PM2.5 and PNC concentrations and contribution of ship traffic and harbour activities

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37 The daily average PM10 concentrations measured by the regional air quality network
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39 (managed by ARPA Puglia - www.arpa.puglia.it) in the city of Brindisi and in particular in the
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41 harbour area were investigated. Specifically, a comparison has been performed between monthly
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43 PM10 concentrations (obtained as a mean from daily average) measured in Terminal Passeggeri,
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45 Costa Morena EST and Costa Morena Diga stations (three stations located inside the harbour area)
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47 and other four stations (Figure 4): Via dei Mille, Via Taranto (located in the urban area) and
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49 Bozzano, Cappuccini (located in the urban background). Ships arrival/departure database has been
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51 built integrating ship traffic data obtained by Port Authority (Autorità Portuale di Brindisi), ship
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53 traffic data collected by MarineTraffic.com and the information of the video camera installed on the
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55 mast of Mobile Laboratory and oriented as in Figure 1b in the sector angle from 290° to 65°. Results
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57 are reported in Figure 4a showing that the minimum and the maximum average PM10
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59 concentrations are both located inside the harbour area. In Figure 4b a comparison of the daily
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61 concentrations at Terminal Passeggeri with the daily ship traffic is reported. No evident correlation
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1 is observed. This means that the analysis of daily measurements, without using specific markers of
2 ship traffic, is not able to put in evidence this contribution. This is compatible with the intermittent
3 nature of emissions associated to ship traffic and related harbour activities. This intermittency
4 makes a relative low average contribution on long-term averages that could be put in evidence using
5 high temporal resolution measurements.
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9 Post-processing of PM_{2.5} and PNC concentrations was performed on 1, 30, 60 minutes
10 averages and daily averages in order to put in evidence short peaks in concentration time series
11 associated to the passage of the ships. Measurements of PM_{2.5} concentrations gave an average of
12 16.7 µg/m³ (median=14.7 µg/m³, inter-quartile-range=12.1 µg/m³). Particle number concentration
13 were, on average, of 14469 particles/cm³ (median=8591 particles/cm³ (inter-quartile-range=9414
14 particles/cm³). Daily averages of PM_{2.5} and PNC were not significantly correlated with ship traffic
15 similarly to what has been observed for PM₁₀. Short-term (1minute) concentrations showed
16 numerous short peaks (durations variable between 10 and 100 minutes) associated to harbour
17 activities and ship traffic (Figure 5). The phases of arrival and departure of the ships, docked at
18 berths in the measurement area, was very clear from this kind of analysis (Figure 5a); it allows to
19 individuate peaks during which the PM_{2.5} concentrations increase typically of 3-4 times and PNC
20 increase up to a factor 10. This means that the contribution of ship traffic is typically larger on PNC
21 with respect to PM_{2.5} indicating that emissions of ship engines are likely dominated by fine and
22 ultrafine particles. With the arrival of a ship at the berth there was a correlated unloading activity of
23 trucks and cars and, at the same way, in the period just before departure, there was a loading
24 activity. In Figure 5b the direct effect on PNC and PM_{2.5} concentrations of this kind of activities
25 can be argued from the peaks following the arrival of the ship at berth, for 30-40 minutes, with a
26 lower concentration, but clearly readable. An important effect on air pollution was also the activities
27 of the ship engine during the phase of hotelling, as can be observed in Figure 5c: generally this
28 contribution was lower respect to the phases of arrival/departure, but it was more extended in time
29 (from 3 to 6 hours). The site is potentially downwind of ship emissions when the wind is blowing
30 from the WNW-ENE (292.5° - 67.5°) sector. In Figure 6a typical hourly pattern of PM_{2.5}
31 concentrations and particle number concentration is reported considering data in the mentioned
32 wind direction sector. In both cases standard errors are reported as error bars. Particle
33 concentrations, both in mass and number, show evident increase in correspondence of wind
34 directions from the harbour area dedicated to ships manoeuvring and hotelling. In particular for
35 particle number concentration daily pattern, two peaks were well marked at 7.00 AM and 6.00 PM.
36 Also PM_{2.5} mass concentration daily pattern shows the same structure, but peak concentration at
37 7.00 AM was more smoothed. In Figure 6b it is reported the daily pattern of ship traffic in terms of
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1 number of vessels and associated gross tonnage. Results indicate that there is a peak in ship traffic,
2 both in number and gross tonnage, during the morning (around 7.00 AM) and it is due especially to
3 arrival at the harbour and a marked peak in the afternoon (6.00 PM) mainly due to departures of
4 ships.
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7 It is clear that the measurement site could be influenced by the direct contribution of ship
8 emissions preferentially at certain periods of the day and from some wind direction sectors. The
9 estimation of the direct contribution on PM_{2.5} and particle number concentration of ship traffic and
10 ship-related activities (loading/unloading of ships that generally happens within the 60 minutes
11 preceding the departure or after the arrival) could be evaluated using high temporal resolution
12 measurements (based on 30 minutes averages) following the approach developed in Contini et al.
13 (2011). In this approach are firstly selected the periods in which the wind is associated to the
14 direction sector between 292.5°-67.5°, corresponding to WNW-ENE, and defining:
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- 23 • C_{DP} as the average concentrations in the selected wind direction sector considering periods
24 influenced by ship emissions;
 - 25 • C_{DSP} as the average concentrations not significantly influenced by ship emissions;
 - 26 • C_D as the average concentration in the specific wind direction sector;
 - 27 • F_P as the frequency of cases influenced by ship emissions.
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35 The direct relative contribution δ could be evaluated as:

$$36 \delta = \frac{(C_{DP} - C_{DSP})F_P}{C_D} = \frac{\Delta_P F_P}{C_D} \quad (3)$$

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41 All concentration data corresponding to a condition of wind calm, wind speed values lower
42 than 0.5 m/s, were eliminated from this analysis. According to Equation (3), the average relative
43 contribution to PM_{2.5} mass concentration, for the Brindisi area in the site considered, was 7.4% (\pm
44 0.5%). For the particle number concentration the contribution was 26% (\pm 1%). Uncertainties were
45 estimated considering the variability in the results when the wind direction sector slightly changed
46 as well as considering the potential influence of the wind calms (in which the wind direction is not
47 properly defined). A further analysis has been performed to evaluate the direct contribution to
48 PM_{2.5} and particle number concentration including harbour activities correlated to ship traffic and
49 vehicular traffic. These activities substantially contribute to emission of particles in the atmosphere.
50 To perform this evaluation the hotelling periods were included in the periods potentially influenced
51 by ship providing that the sites was downwind of the different docks present in the area. Two wind
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1 direction sectors associated to docks were individuated. The first in the wind direction sector from
2 292.5° to 10° and the second in the sector from 15° to 60°. Cars and trucks traffic has been
3 evaluated by counting traffic, associated to loading and unloading of ships, from the images
4 provided by the video camera in each 30-minute period. A threshold of at least 10 vehicles (in the
5 30-minute period) was considered to assume a possible influence on the measurements. When the
6 contribution of harbour activities related to ship traffic is included in the calculation the total
7 contribution (ship traffic plus harbour-related activities) becomes 9.3% ($\pm 0.5\%$) for PM_{2.5} and
8 39% ($\pm 1\%$) for PNC. In Table 2 a comparison of the relative contribution of ship traffic to
9 atmospheric PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PNC concentrations observed in Brindisi and in other harbour areas
10 is reported.
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20 **7. Contribution of the harbour/industrial emissions on PAHs concentrations**

21 In Table 3 results from sampling are summarized. In general, concentration of Σ PAHs ranged
22 from 1.10 ng/m³ to 12.6 ng/m³, with 3.89 ng/m³ as average. This result is comparable to that found
23 in other port cities as Venice (Contini et al., 2011) and in the urban areas in Tuscany (0.92-13
24 ng/m³) (Cincinelli et al., 2007), lower than PAHs concentration measured in the neighbourhood of
25 the Kaohsiung Harbour of Taiwan (Lai et al., 2013) and in other urban areas in Portugal (average of
26 70 ng/m³) (Slezakova et al., 2013) and Egypt (330-1770 ng/m³) (Khairy et al., 2013). A higher
27 concentration was obtained considering only samples from the harbour/industrial sector: 5.34 ng/m³
28 (1.85-9.26 ng/m³). Benzo[a]pyrene concentrations were always under the Italian limit value of 1
29 ng/m³ (Legislative Decree n.155, 2010).
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38 PAHs are predominant in the gaseous form: only 19% and 30% of Σ PAHs was associated to
39 particles, during the 360° and the harbour/industrial sector samplings, respectively. Among gaseous
40 PAHs (g-PAHs), in air coming from all directions, the main contributors to the total concentration
41 were FLA (34% of Σ g-PAHs), PYR (26% of Σ g-PAHs) and PHE (22% of Σ g-PAHs). PHE
42 represents the most abundant congener in gas from the harbour/industrial area (40% of Σ g-PAHs),
43 followed by FLA (19% of Σ g-PAHs) and PYR (18% of Σ g-PAHs). Particulate matter is
44 characterized by a more complex profile: the most present particulate PAHs (p-PAHs) from all
45 directions were IcdP (20% of Σ p-PAHs) and BghiP (18% of Σ p-PAHs); in harbour/industrial
46 particulate PYR (31% of Σ p-PAHs) and PHE (22% of Σ p-PAHs) were the most abundant PAHs.
47 Globally, a relative increase of FL and PHE in harbour/industrial air has been observed (FL: from
48 2% to 10%; PHE: from 19% to 35%): it is significant because these congeners have been identified
49 as the most abundant PAHs in emission from ships (Cooper, 2003). PAHs concentration in harbour
50 air was compared to emission from various kind of ships that used different fuels, measured by
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1 Cooper (2003). Figure 7 shows that there was a very good correlation (C: 0.979) between the profile
2 of PAHs concentration (gas plus particulate) in harbour/industrial air and the emission of a chemical
3 tanker that uses low-sulphur marine oil. This is an indication that ship emissions play an important
4 role in determining PAHs concentrations in wind coming from the harbour/industrial sector.
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7 As in other studies (Cincinelli et al., 2007; Hassan and Khoder, 2012) a strong correlation
8 between PAHs distribution and molecular weight has been observed: low molecular weight PAHs
9 are generally more volatile than high molecular weight PAHs, thus it is more probable to find them
10 in the gaseous form.
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13 In Table 3 the estimation of the contribution of the ship traffic, the harbour activities and other
14 sources in the harbour/industrial wind sector on PAHs concentration is reported. Both the local and
15 the general effects (equations 1 and 2), applied on gaseous, particulate and total (gas plus
16 particulate) PAHs were included. The results showed an average local effect of the harbour of 26%
17 (9-48%) and a general effect ranging from 29% to 87% (56% on average). These results can be
18 interpreted as follows: an hypothetical person staying on the roof of the ASI building during the
19 sampling inhaled on average 26% of PAHs coming from the harbour/industrial sector and the
20 remaining 74% of PAHs coming from other directions. This contribution depends both on the
21 sources present in the analyzed sector (ship traffic and harbour activities), and on the occurrence of
22 wind blowing from the harbour area (5 hours/day, on average during the sampling period). The
23 general estimated contribution of the harbour and other sources in the sector under analysis,
24 considered the variability of the occurrence of wind directions, was 56%. There was not a
25 significant difference between the contribution of the harbour/industrial sector on gaseous and
26 particulate PAHs. Since g-PAHs represent from 70 to 81% of \sum PAHs, the contribution of the
27 harbour/industrial emissions on gaseous PAHs was very close to the effect on total PAHs.
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31 The general effect of the harbour has been calculated on single congeners. For every PAHs
32 the contributions on gaseous and particulate phase have been separated (Figure 8).
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35 From Figure 8, it can be observed that the harbour influenced congeners concentration in a
36 different way. The major contribution (>60%) was on ACY, ACE, FL, PHE and BaP. ANT, FLA,
37 PYR and IcdP seemed to be generated both from the harbour and from other sources in the opposite
38 sector ($40\% \leq \chi \leq 50\%$). The remaining congeners were coming to a less extend from the harbour and
39 can be produced mostly by various sources in the urban or industrial area. Among congeners
40 characterized by the highest contribution from the harbour, FL and PHE are significant because
41 their presence can be related to ship traffic, as mentioned before. Great concern is given by the
42 contribution of the harbour on BaP, that is considered a certain carcinogenic compound for humans
43 by IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer) (Iarc, 2012). As expected, low molecular
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weight congeners were characterized by a contribution of the harbour on gaseous phase that was higher than the contribution on particulate matter, because of their gas-particle distribution.

8. Health risk assessment

Benzo[a]pyrene has been regarded by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the most appropriate indicator in order to evaluate the carcinogenicity of PAHs in air; but the use of BaP concentration alone will probably underestimate the carcinogenic potential of airborne PAHs mixtures, since co-occurring substances are also carcinogenic (WHO, 1998). Despite benzo[a]pyrene concentration was under the threshold value imposed by Italian legislation, the contribution (62%) of the harbour/industrial emissions to this congener makes it worthwhile to carry out an assessment on the health risk associated to such mixture of PAHs. The risk of inhalation of carcinogenic PAHs in the study area was estimated by using toxic equivalent factors (TEFs): multiplying the absolute concentration of every congener by its corresponding TEF value, BaP equivalent (BaP_{eq}) concentration can be obtained. In Table 4 average total concentrations of PAHs (gas, particulate and total) were used to calculate average BaP_{eq} concentration of PAHs referring to air from all directions and air from the harbour/industrial sector.

Results showed that air from the harbour/industrial sector was characterized by a total carcinogenic activity (0.137 ng/m³) a bit higher than generic air of Brindisi (0.119 ng/m³). In both cases the most important contributor to the TCA was BaP. In air from the harbour/industrial its absolute concentration and the relative contribution to TCA was higher than in air from all directions, but the decreasing of several congeners concentration characterized by medium (BaA, BbF; TEF: 0.1) and high (DahA; TEF: 1) carcinogenicity in air balanced the increasing of BaP concentration, permitting TCA to remain at an acceptable value. TCA detected values from both samplings are under the Italian limit threshold for BaP (1 ng/m³) (Legislative Decree n.155, 2010). Despite the low content of total PAHs in particulate, aerosol showed a TCA 3-4 times higher than that calculated for gaseous phase. Indeed, particulate phase is rich in heaviest PAHs, which are characterized by a higher carcinogenic activity. In gas phase high concentration of less dangerous low molecular weight congeners have been found.

9. Conclusions

The emissions from ships may compromise the air quality while hotelling or manoeuvring in harbours and while transiting along the coast. In this work it is reported an assessment of the impact of ship traffic and related harbour activities on PM_{2.5}, particle number concentrations (PNC) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) concentrations in the port-city of Brindisi (South Italy).

1 Ships emissions during their phases of manoeuvring and hotelling show a very clear daily
2 pattern, with two distinct peaks, strictly correlated with harbour ship traffic pattern. The ship traffic
3 contribution to atmospheric aerosol is made of numerous short peaks of concentration associated to
4 harbour activities. During these peaks PM2.5 concentrations increase typically of 3-4 times and
5 PNC increase typically up to a factor 10. The average relative contribution estimated to PM2.5 mass
6 concentration, for the Brindisi area in the site considered, was 7.4% ($\pm 0.5\%$). The PNC
7 contribution was 26% ($\pm 1\%$). An analysis was performed to evaluate the total (ship traffic and
8 harbour related activities such as loading/unloading and hotelling) direct contribution to PM2.5 and
9 PNC. The total average contribution was 9.3% ($\pm 0.5\%$) to PM2.5 concentration and 39% ($\pm 1\%$) to
10 PNC concentration.

11 Air from the harbour/industrial sector was richer in PAHs (5.34 ng/m^3) than generic air of
12 Brindisi (3.89 ng/m^3). Benzo[a]pyrene concentration was under the Italian legislation limit of 1
13 ng/m^3 , in both cases. The most present compounds were phenanthrene, fluoranthene and pyrene, but
14 the congeners profiles were different in the two typologies of samples: in air from the
15 harbour/industrial an increase of the relative concentration of phenanthrene and fluorene, which are
16 the most abundant PAHs from ship emissions, has been observed. A comparison between congeners
17 profile in air from the harbour/industrial sector and ship emissions gave a very good correlation.
18 Results showed that PAHs are mostly in the gas phase. The gas-particle distribution was
19 characterized by the lighter PAHs most located in the gaseous phase and higher molecular weight
20 congeners mostly in particulate phase. The local effect of the harbour in the sampling site from June
21 to September 2012 (ϵ) was 26% (9-48%); the general effect of the harbour (χ) was 56% (29-87%).
22 The harbour influenced PAHs concentration especially contributing to acenaphthylene, acenaphthene,
23 fluorene, phenanthrene and benzo[a]pyrene. Total Carcinogenic Activity calculated using TEFs was
24 slightly higher in samples from the harbour/industrial sector than in those from 360° sampling; but
25 TCAs were both below the Italian limit value for benzo[a]pyrene. Particulate matter was
26 characterized by a higher carcinogenic activity than gaseous phase, due to the gas-particle
27 distribution of congeners.

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FIGURE 1

Figure 1. Satellite map from Google Earth© of Brindisi harbor showing: a) the relative location of the city, the harbour, the airport, industrial areas and measurement sites. b) a zoom of Mobile Lab position (red point) with the specification of the wind direction sector used in data selection (wind direction from 297.5° to 67.5°).

FIGURE 2

Figure 2. a) Fast optical detector pDR-1200 (1Hz) to measure PM_{2.5} mass concentrations and its aerated outdoor box. b) Condensation Particle Counter (CPC) (Grimm Aerosol Model 5.403) which measured the total particle number concentrations. Air sample went through a dryer to reduce water vapor concentration. Dryer was placed at right of the CPC in the figure. c) At ASI site, two high-volume samplers (AirFlowPUF, Analitica Strumenti, Italy and Tish Environmental Inc., USA), one of them equipped with a wind selective device.

FIGURE 3

Figure 3. Wind rose for the complete period of measurement at Mobile Laboratory site

FIGURE 4

Figure 4. a) Monthly average for PM10 concentration for different measurement sites in the harbour area and in urban or suburban area of Brindisi. Error bars show the variability represented by standard error. b) PM10 concentration (daily average) at Terminal Passeggeri and the cumulative daily gross tonnage.

FIGURE 5

Figure 5. Example of PM2.5 and PNC peaks associated to ship arrival and departure operation for 19th July (a) and 22th July. In b) it is shown PM2.5 and PNC during a phase of unloading of trucks and cars from the docked ships. In c) it is shown PM2.5 and PNC during the phase of hostelling of the ship between arrival and departure.

FIGURE 6

Figure 6. a) Daily pattern for PM2.5 and PNC concentrations. The error bars represent the standard errors. Data refer to the wind direction sector between WNW and ENE. b) Daily pattern of ship traffic in terms of number of vessels and cumulative gross tonnage.

FIGURE 7

Figure 7. Comparison between PAHs concentration in harbor/industrial air (gas plus particulate) and emission from a chemical tanker that uses low-sulphur marine oil (F/AE232%, by Cooper (2003). C indicates the Pearson's correlation coefficient

FIGURE 8

Figure 8. General effect of the harbour/industrial sector (χ , %) for all PAHs congeners in gaseous and particulate phase.

TABLE 1

DATE Samples	Sampler 1: All directions (m³)	Sampler 2: Harbour/Industrial sector (m³)	DATE Blanks
20-22 June	843.3	129.5	
22-25 June	1246.6	116.9	22 June
25-27 June	843.1	207.2	
29 June-2 July	1269.8	384.2	29 June
6-9 July	1266.9	144.2	
9-11 July	850.5	338.7	9 July
11-13 July	841.8	149.0	
16-18 July	842.3	87.3	16 July
18-20 July	833.2	163.1	
25-27 July	787.1	105.2	24 July
27-31 August	1475.6	338.0	
31 August-4 September	1475.3	57.4	31 August
4-7 September	1267.8	198.1	

Table 1. Sampling dates and volumes for PAHs.

TABLE 2

	PM10 or PM2.5	PNC	
Brindisi (Italy)	7.4% (±0.5%)	26% (±1%)	Result from this work
Venezia (Italy, 3 sites)	1- 8 %	-	Contini et al., 2011
Halifax (Canada)	3.4 %	-	Gibson et al., 2013
Cork (Ireland)	1.5 %	18%	Healy et al., 2010
Melilla (Spain)	2%	-	Viana et al., 2009
Algeciras (Spain)	3 - 7 % 5 - 10 %	-	Pandolfi et al., 2011
California (USA, 10 sites)	1.4 - 8.8 %	-	Agrawal et al., 2009
Other (England, Italy and Portugal)	5 - 10 %	-	Fagerli and Tarrason, 2001
Barcelona (Spain)	5%	-	Amato et al., 2011
Shangai (China)	4.2%	-	Zhao et al., 2013

Table 2. Inter-comparison of ship contribution to atmospheric aerosol evaluated at Brindisi with those of other European and extra-European harbour areas. PM10 are reported in bold.

TABLE 3

Sampler 1: All directions			
PAHs	Gas	Particulate	Total
ACY	0.00285 (n.d.-0.00681)	0.00160 (n.d.- 0.0134)	0.00445 (n.d.- 0.0199)
ACE	0.00330 (n.d.-0.0195)	0.00139 (n.d.-0.0101)	0.00470 (n.d.- 0.0195)
FL	0.0650 (0.0305-0.163)	0.00227 (n.d.-0.0131)	0.0673 (0.0305-0.163)
PHE	0.682 (0.218-1.42)	0.0544 (n.d.-0.424)	0.736 (0.218-1.49)
ANT	0.0229 (0.00427-0.0766)	0.00777 (n.d.-0.0784)	0.0307 (0.00598-0.123)
FLA	1.09 (0.119-4.53)	0.0508 (0.0207-0.0952)	1.14 (0.177-4.63)
PYR	0.825 (0.140-2.95)	0.0742 (0.00613-0.257)	0.899 (0.175-3.21)
BaA	0.110 (0.00517-0.521)	0.0238 (0.00957-0.0705)	0.134 (0.0193-0.591)
CHR	0.274 (0.0290-1.18)	0.0600 (0.0304-0.146)	0.334 (0.0655-1.33)
BbF	0.0621 (0.00188-0.289)	0.0862 (0.0320-0.286)	0.148 (0.0342-0.484)
BkF	0.0180 (0.000619-0.107)	0.0289 (0.0103-0.0813)	0.0469 (0.0126-0.144)
BaP	0.00268 (0.000983-0.00550)	0.0439 (0.0209-0.0931)	0.0466 (0.0228-0.0943)
BghiP	0.00222 (n.d.-0.0107)	0.129 (0.0230-0.397)	0.131 (0.0242-0.399)
IcdP	0.0109 (n.d.-0.0652)	0.143 (0.0175-0.382)	0.154 (0.0212-0.382)
DahA	n.d.	0.0158 (n.d.-0.0500)	0.0158 (n.d.- 0.0500)
Σ 15PAHs	3.17 (0.568-11.0)	0.723 (0.227-1.65)	3.89 (1.10-12.6)
Sampler 2: Harbour/Industrial sector			
PAHs	Gas	Particulate	Total
ACY	0.0282 (n.d.-0.0972)	0.00578 (n.d.-0.0414)	0.0340 (n.d.- 0.112)
ACE	0.0536 (n.d.-0.332)	0.0103 (n.d.-0.0909)	0.0639 (n.d.- 0.332)
FL	0.512 (0.0810-0.889)	0.00910 (n. d.-0.0615)	0.521 (0.0890-0.889)
PHE	1.51 (0.308-2.81)	0.353 (n.d.-1.790)	1.87 (0.308-4.11)
ANT	0.0550 (n.d.-0.164)	0.0393 (n.d.-0.191)	0.0943 (n.d.- 0.355)
FLA	0.702 (0.145-2.39)	0.117 (n.d.-0.250)	0.819 (0.287-2.45)
PYR	0.681 (0.0886-1.57)	0.498 (n.d.-1.85)	1.18 (0.107-2.89)
BaA	0.0214 (n.d.-0.199)	0.0214 (0.00631-0.0713)	0.0428 (0.00715-0.271)
CHR	0.108 (0.0147-0.602)	0.0741 (0.0341-0.173)	0.182 (0.0568-0.775)
BbF	0.00989 (n.d.-0.0419)	0.0592 (0.0236-0.210)	0.0691 (0.0251-0.210)
BkF	0.00389 (n.d.-0.0296)	0.0205 (0.00791-0.0714)	0.0244 (0.00794-0.0714)
BaP	0.0177 (n.d.-0.0780)	0.0630 (0.0243-0.131)	0.0807 (0.0279-0.177)
BghiP	0.00721 (n.d.-0.0386)	0.0725 (n.d.-0.234)	0.0797 (0.00102-0.243)
IcdP	0.0335 (n.d.-0.203)	0.241 (n.d.-1.18)	0.275 (n.d.- 1.22)
DahA	0.000211 (n.d.-0.00147)	0.00703 (n.d.-0.0359)	0.00724 (n.d.- 0.0359)
Σ 15PAHs	3.75 (0.661-7.82)	1.59 (0.140-4.24)	5.34 (1.85-9.26)

Table 3. PAHs concentration (ng/m³) detected in summer 2012, in gaseous and particulate phases. Mean value (range). n.d.: no detectable

TABLE 4

	Gas	Particulate	Total (gas + particulate)
Local effect, ε (%)	24 (9-45)	35 (3-57)	26 (9-48)
General effect, χ (%)	54 (21-86)	62 (11-91)	56 (29-87)

Table 4. Local (ε , %) and general (χ , %) effect of the harbour/industrial emissions on gaseous, particulate and total (gas plus particulate) PAHs content of the territory. Medium value (range).

TABLE 5

PAH	TEF	All directions air			Harbour/Industrial sector air		
		Gas	Particulate	Total (Gas + particulate)	Gas	Particulate	Total (Gas + particulate)
ACY	0.001	0.00285	0.00160	0.00445	0.0282	0.00578	0.0340
ACE	0.001	0.00330	0.00139	0.00470	0.0536	0.0103	0.0639
FL	0.001	0.0650	0.00227	0.0673	0.512	0.00910	0.521
PHE	0.001	0.682	0.0544	0.736	1.51	0.353	1.87
ANT	0.01	0.229	0.0777	0.307	0.550	0.393	0.943
FLA	0.001	1.09	0.0508	1.14	0.702	0.117	0.819
PYR	0.001	0.825	0.0742	0.899	0.681	0.498	1.18
BaA	0.1	11.0	2.38	13.4	2.14	2.14	4.28
CHR	0.01	2.74	0.600	3.34	1.08	0.741	1.82
BbF	0.1	6.21	8.62	14.8	0.989	5.92	6.91
BkF	0.1	1.80	2.89	4.69	0.389	2.05	2.44
BaP	1	2.68	43.9	46.6	17.7	63.0	80.7
BghiP	0.01	0.0222	1.29	1.31	0.0721	0.725	0.797
IcdP	0.1	1.09	14.3	15.4	3.35	24.1	27.5
DahA	1	0.0483	15.8	15.8	0.211	7.03	7.24
TCA	-	28.5	90.0	119	29.9	107	137

Table 5. Benzo[a]pyrene equivalent (BaP_{eq}) concentration (pg/m³) for every PAH in gas, particulate and total (gas plus particulate phases), in samples of air from all directions and air from the harbour/industrial sector.